

BLACK CURRANT (RIBES NIGRUM) GROWING TECHNOLOGY

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Annotation: Blackcurrant leaves, fruits and preparations are used to treat scurvy and other hypo and avitaminosis diseases. Its fruit is used as a diuretic and diuretic in folk medicine. It is very important to grow it.

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Currants begin to bear fruit in the 3rd-4th year. It gives abundant harvest for 10-15 years. Fruits of 20-25 years of life are very small. Currants begin to bear fruit 2 years after planting. It is propagated from cuttings by dividing the bushes into several pieces. Karakat in regions with high air temperature and low soil moisture. In the conditions of the Republic of Uzbekistan, black, red and golden varieties of currants are widespread. Under the conditions of Uzbekistan, golden currant gives a good harvest. Because golden currants have a deep winter dormancy period, they will not come out of dormancy even though winter conditions will rise to 67 degrees and have sufficient temperatures to grow. Because of this, currants can easily withstand the cold. Even at 30-32°C, as its roots reach a depth of 2 m. it does not wither because it can use underground water.[1,4,5]

It is very important to be able to choose the right land for currants. This plant grows well on flat, fertile sandy soil with a slope of up to 10°S facing west

or north-west. Currant planted lands should be well supplied with water. Planting. Currants are propagated from cuttings in spring or autumn by dividing the bush into several pieces or by cutting. Currants should be planted before frost if they are planted in autumn, but after the plant stops growing, and if it is propagated in spring, before the buds emerge. In the spring, currants grow quickly and have time to produce leaves. Therefore, it is advisable to plant currants in autumn. Broken and diseased branches should not be taken for planting. In addition, uncoarsened branches are selected for planting. The length of the selected branches should not be longer than 15-20 cm. Due to the fact that currant grows and thickens quickly in water-supplied conditions, the distance between the rows is 3 m, and the distance between the bushes is 1.5-2 m. In this case, the number of plants in one hectare field can be 1666-2222 bushes. Cuttings or pieces of plant bushes are planted in previously prepared pits (40 x 40, 60 x 60 cm). If there is no organic fertilizer, 6-7 kg of humus and 200-300 g of mineral fertilizer are added to each pit. 68 After the pits are filled with soil, the seedlings are watered through pre-prepared watering cans. [1,3,5]

Then, leaving 3-4 buds in the upper part of each pen, the upper part of the branches is trimmed and mulched with humus or manure. Before planting seedlings, 800-1000 kg of superphosphate is mixed with 40-100 tons of manure, depending on the level of soil fertility. 60 kg of nitrogen, 120 kg of phosphorus and 30 kg of potassium are added to the currant field every year. Phosphorous and potash fertilizers are applied during fall plowing. Half of the nitrogen fertilizers are given in the spring at the beginning of vegetation, and the other half at the end of flowering - during fruiting. Approximately half of the fertilizer is applied directly to the base of the plants for two years after planting, and in the remaining years, it is applied to the entire field. Also, during the first two years after planting, organic fertilizers are applied around the plant in the form of 5-10

kg of mulch in a diameter of 50-100 cm, and between the rows in the amount of 20-30 t in the third and fourth years. is put in the whole field. It plays an important role in providing water and nutrients to plant balls and provides great opportunities for good growth and development of plants. Currant vegetation support, watered from 5 to 15 times to every time. Propagate branches with more fruit and growth buds in autumn. that is, the connected plant is cut.[2,4]

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